

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Post-Return Practices and Experiences

WP8 Comparative Report – Survey Study: Afghanistan, Iraq,
Nigeria and Tunisia

Author(s):

Hidayet Sıddıkoğlu¹ & Andreas Önver Cetrez²

¹ Bilim Organization, ² Uppsala University

D8.2 - February 2026

Funded by
the European Union

Deliverable information

Project acronym	GAPs - De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond
Project no.	101094341
WP	8
Deliverable title	Post-Return Practices and Experiences: WP8 Comparative Report – Survey Study: Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria and Tunisia
Deliverable type	R – Document, report
Version	V1
Date	February 2026
Responsible partners	Bilim Organization and Uppsala University
Authors	Hidayet Siddikoğlu & Andreas Önver Cetrez
Dissemination level	Public

Revision history

Version	Date	Authors	Changes
v1	05-01-2026	The authors	Reviewed by Z. Sahin-Mencutek and S. Barthoma
v2	10-02-2026	The authors	Resubmission of revised, final draft to GAPs coordinators

© Bilim & Uppsala University

This research was conducted under the Horizon Europe project ‘GAPS: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond’ (101094341). The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the authors. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to the authors at: h.siddikoglu22@gmail.com and onver.cetrez@teol.uu.se

Cite as:

Siddikoğlu, H. and Cetrez, A.O. (2026) WP7: Post-Return Practices and Experiences: WP8 Comparative Report – Survey Study: Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria and Tunisia, in *GAPs Working paper 2026/11*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1876723

Contents

ABOUT THE PROJECT.....	4
ABSTRACT.....	5
1. INTRODUCTION.....	5
2. METHODOLOGY.....	6
2.1 AFGHANISTAN.....	7
2.2 IRAQ.....	7
2.3 NIGERIA.....	8
2.4 TUNISIA.....	8
3. DEMOGRAPHICS.....	9
4. TIME AND COUNTRY OF RETURN.....	10
5. THE ROUTE OF RETURN.....	11
6. FORCED OR VOLUNTARY RETURN.....	13
7. DETENTION EXPERIENCES ABROAD.....	13
8. SOURCE OF FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR RETURN.....	15
9. LIKELIHOOD OF LEGAL OR ILLEGAL MIGRATION.....	17
10. HOPE AND RESILIENCE.....	18
10.1 HOPE.....	18
10.2 RESILIENCE.....	18
11. DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	20
REFERENCES.....	22
APPENDIX 1: HOPE AND RESILIENCE SCALES AFGHANISTAN CASE STUDY.....	24

About the project

GAPs is a three-year Horizon Europe research project funded by the European Commission (Grant Agreement No. 101094341). It began on 1 March 2023 and will run until 28 February 2026. The project examines how decisions and policies on “return” are made—that is, how people who have migrated are expected, encouraged, or required to return to their country of origin, and what happens during and after return.

Rather than viewing return policymaking as something designed and implemented only by governments or international organisations, GAPs broadens the analytical lens by incorporating multiple perspectives, including those of returnees themselves. In particular, the project investigates the complex relationships and interactions among the actors involved in return processes, including state institutions, international organisations, NGOs, local authorities, communities, and returnees’ families. It also considers both “internal” dynamics within countries of origin and “external” dynamics shaped by other countries, border policies, and international agreements that influence return governance.

Specifically, GAPs:

- identifies missing links in the European Union’s return policy, considering both internal and external dimensions;
- explores factors that facilitate or hinder international cooperation; and
- documents returnees’ experiences and examines the factors shaping their resilience, aspirations, and hope in the face of adversity.

The GAPs project is organised into 11 Work Packages. Each Work Package addresses a specific aspect of return and reintegration, and together they examine how existing laws, policies, and institutions shape the way return is managed in practice. Overall, the project aims to identify what works well, where the main structural and operational gaps lie, and how return governance can be made more effective and humane. To achieve this, GAPs combines policy and institutional analysis with evidence from returnees themselves, capturing their lived experiences, resilience, and hopes under challenging conditions.

The research covers 14 countries: Afghanistan, Germany, Georgia, Greece, Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Poland, Sweden, Tunisia, and Türkiye.

Abstract

The key objectives of this comparative report are to identify similarities and differences in structural conditions, demographic profiles, and return and reintegration experiences, including levels of hope and resilience during the reintegration phase across four key returnee countries: Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, and Tunisia. The analysis is based on data from 1118 returnee interviews conducted across aforementioned four countries. Despite geographical and structural differences finding suggested most returnees were forcibly returned and experienced detentions in host countries before being returned to their countries of habitual residence. Yet, returnees across these countries exhibited distinct demographic profiles: Afghanistan had the highest share of young, married, and economically active returnees, while Nigeria had the largest proportion of older returnees, and Tunisia had the lowest proportion of married returnees. These demographic differences suggest variation in returnees' experiences and reintegration trajectories, including condition under which hope and resilience are developed and maintained. Moreover, structural conditions that shape access to state and non-state reintegration assistance differently affect reintegration processes across the four countries. This report makes a significant contribution to return migration scholarship by documenting returnees' lived experiences and reintegration trajectories in the Global South.

1. Introduction

This report focuses on Work Package Eight (WP8), which examines returnees' experiences in Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, and Tunisia. It presents a comparative assessment of findings from these four countries to identify similarities and differences in returnees' lived experiences across diverse return contexts. The analysis covers demographic characteristics of returnees, the countries they are returned, the experiences of detention in the pre-return stage, the voluntariness aspect in the return process and sources of financial support enabling return as well as the reintegration indicators such as access to livelihood and employment, housing, well being. The survey includes 1118 participants in total, while 416 in Afghanistan, 250 in Iraq, 288 in Nigeria, 164 in Tunisia. (for detailed demographics about gender, age, marital status see Table 1).

Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, and Tunisia¹ selected for researching returnees' experiences for two main reasons. First, they are among the principal countries of return for people returned from Europe across the Middle East and Africa. Second, examining these four settings enables a comparative analysis of returnees' experiences under different structural conditions. These cases illustrate how formal policies and programmes are translated into operational decisions on the ground (for example, who receives assistance, how services are coordinated, and what conditions returnees face upon arrival). This approach also allows the report to assess how

¹ For details on each country refer to country reports published on GAPs official website. For details on Afghanistan see 'Post-return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Afghanistan', available at <https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/practices-and-experiences-of-returnees-in-afghanistan>; For Iraq see 'Return Migration Infrastructures in Iraq – Country Dossier', available at <https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-infrastructures-in-iraq-country-dossier>; For Nigeria see 'Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Nigeria', available at <https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/post-return-practices-experiences-of-returnees-nigeria>; and for Tunisia see 'Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Tunisia', available at <https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/postreturn-practices-experiences-of-returnees-tunisia>.

variation in institutional capacity, coordination arrangements, and local reception contexts influences reintegration trajectories and outcomes.

This paper draws on the country reports produced by consortium partners under WP8. Each country report is based on field surveys conducted under varying structural and environmental constraints, which shaped both access to respondents and the final sample sizes across context (Tunisia 164 interview; Iraq 250 interviews; Nigeria 288 interviews; and Afghanistan 416 interviews). Similarly, the demographic characteristics of respondents, particularly age, marital and engagement status, education, and gender varied across the four cases. These differences in both sample size and respondent profiles constitute a key limitation for cross-country comparison, as they constrain the robustness and interpretability of comparative analysis of psychometric scales such as hope and resilience.

2. Methodology

This report is derived from structured field surveys with 1118 participants in total. Survey is preceded by pilot interviews conducted in each of the four countries, to contextualise the questionnaire and generate empirical evidence on returnees' experiences and the implementation of return governance in practice. As part of a pilot study, the validity and reliability of different scales were assessed, with a focus on returnees' hope, resilience, and depression. Obtained results from Afghanistan² and Nigeria³ indicated that all measurement scales exhibited high reliability.

Throughout the development and implementation of the field survey, partners in Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, and Tunisia held a series of coordination meetings to ensure consistency and quality across countries. These meetings covered the design and refinement of the survey instrument, procedures for obtaining ethical clearance in each country, fieldwork ethics and safeguarding, data protection requirements, and protocols for data management and analysis. They also provided a platform for jointly reviewing and revising the questionnaire, discussing operational challenges emerging during fieldwork, and aligning analytical procedures to support cross-country comparability. The coordination process was led by Uppsala University.

Due to structural and regulatory differences, partners in each country were subject to distinct procedural requirements and access conditions as will be explained below. As a result, data-collection approaches, sampling strategies, and the number of participants included in the field surveys varied substantially across the four countries.

Data protection is of the utmost importance in survey work. GAPs organised several workshops on data protection and data management practices at different occasions, including sessions led by other work packages (e.g. Work Packages 1, 4 and 11), to provide practical guidance to all partners on how to protect, store, and manage research data. In addition, BILIM shared a recorded training session—published on YouTube—on analysing GAPs data using R (GAPS Classical Test Theory - CTT),⁴ and also produced a manual on data

² In Afghanistan analysis revealed that all three scales met the minimum level of reliability: hope = .81; resilience = .89; and depression = .84.

³ In Nigeria analysis revealed that all three scales met the minimum level of reliability: hope = .65; resilience = .80; and depression = .79.

⁴ BILIM, GAPS CTT Analysis available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o-VYy3eyIi4>

management and report development. Across the project, country teams received multiple training sessions on data protection and management before and during the fieldwork period. All teams applied stringent data protection measures in line with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

In the following section, the methodological framework for each country is briefly outlined.

2.1 Afghanistan

In Afghanistan, Bilim Organization for Research and Social Studies (hereafter BILIM) formalised cooperation through a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with the Ministry of Refugees and Repatriation. This was followed by securing an ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board at the Ministry of Public Health, through the submission of an application that included the survey questionnaire. This agreement enabled access to administrative records, including a list of approximately 210,000 returnees who returned to Afghanistan between 2013 and 2023, which was used as the sampling frame for outreach and survey recruitment. Using a randomly generated list of 210,000 returnees (between 2013 and 2023), 416 Afghan returnees were randomly selected and surveyed across four provinces of Kabul (100), Herat (106), Balkh (102), and Kandahar (108) using a two-stage stratified design; random selection of settlements, followed by random selection of returnees within those settlements. Data were collected through in-person interviews conducted with SurveyCTO by seven trained interviewers between 27 December 2023 and 17 January 2024. A sample size (416) was statistically reasonable for many types of survey analysis, particularly for estimating proportions with a 95% confidence level and a margin of error of approximately $\pm 5\%$, assuming a reasonably homogeneous population.

At the operational level, BILIM established coordination with the provincial directorates of MoRR and the provincial police departments under the Ministry of Interior. The fieldwork nevertheless faced several institutional and administrative challenges. For example, despite holding an ethical clearance certificate, the survey was initially not permitted in Kandahar. To address this, BILIM initiated additional communication and coordination with the Kandahar Governorate and subsequently secured the required clearance to conduct fieldwork in the province. Similar challenges also emerged in Balkh, Kabul, and Herat, where additional coordination and meetings with relevant authorities were required to resolve operational constraints and enable data collection. Another key challenge was recruiting female staff and securing access to female returnees for interviews. As a result, the number of female returnees interviewed remained lower than the number of male respondents.

2.2 Iraq

In Iraq, HHRO adopted a two-stage procedure to conduct the field survey. First, it secured ethical clearance from the Catholic University in Erbil, ensuring that the study complied with relevant data protection and research ethics requirements, including the principles of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Second, it submitted a formal authorisation request to the Non-Governmental Organizations Directorate within the Council of Ministers' General Secretariat. This submission included the survey questionnaire jointly developed by WP8 partners and obtained permission to implement data collection in the field. Feedback from the Directorate requesting further contextualisation of the questionnaire was received on 15 August 2024. In parallel, HHRO approached the Directorate as well as a range of national and international non-state organisations to request access to administrative lists of returnees; however, none of the institutions shared such lists.

Against this backdrop, HHRO developed an alternative recruitment strategy. In May 2024, it created a dedicated Facebook platform through which returnees could voluntarily register and provide basic information, including their country of return and year of return to Iraq. Through this mechanism, 400 returnees registered on the platform. From this pool, 300 individuals were selected based on two eligibility criteria: (i) return from Europe and (ii) return within the past 10 years. Of the 300 eligible individuals contacted, 250 agreed to participate in the field survey. No digital platform was used due to technical constraints; data were collected manually using printed paper questionnaires.

Survey participants were then stratified across six governorates, with the largest share interviewed in Baghdad (n = 125), followed by Nineveh (n = 36), Erbil (n = 31), and smaller numbers in Duhok, Sulaymaniyah, and Kirkuk.

Similar to the case of Afghanistan, HHRO in Iraq faced multiple institutional challenges in accessing returnee lists and reaching a sufficient number of female returnees. These constraints also complicated coordination with local authorities, particularly in efforts to locate and recruit returnees across the governorates with the largest returnee populations. The absence of an administrative sampling frame made it difficult and time-consuming to identify and contact the target population and to ensure balanced geographical coverage.

2.3 Nigeria

Fieldwork was conducted between May 2023 and February 2025. A total of 288 returnees were surveyed across four key urban centres, Lagos, Benin, Abuja, and Owerri, and the data were analysed in SPSS using descriptive and inferential statistics. Survey recruitment relied on chain-referral (snowball) sampling, supported by civil society organisations. No digital platform was used due to technical constraints; data were collected manually using printed paper questionnaires.

Evidence was drawn from meeting notes and presentations of Nigeria's Technical Working Group on Migration, as well as stakeholder roundtables organised under the GAPs Project. A focus group discussion was held in Lagos in February 2024 at the Patriotic Citizens Initiative premises; it lasted approximately 90 minutes and included 10 participants (5 men and 5 women) aged 25–40, all of whom had returned within the previous 10 years. The FGD explored gendered dimensions of return, stigma, resilience, depression, hope, and aspirations for re-migration.

All research activities followed established ethical standards: informed consent was obtained, participation was voluntary, and identifiers were removed from datasets. Data were securely stored and used only for research purposes, and sensitive topics (e.g. trauma, detention, deportation) were handled with care. Institutional clearance was obtained from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka (Strategic Contacts, Ethics and Publications), via the Population–Environment–Development Research Group, and ethical compliance was aligned with Horizon Europe research ethics requirements.

2.4 Tunisia

In the absence randomly listed national databases on returnees, the Tunisian fieldwork could not draw on a pre-existing probability-based sampling frame. Instead, the survey team employed two complementary population outreach strategies. First, in collaboration with institutional partners, it obtained an administrative list of returnees and conducted 85

interviews with individuals selected from that list. Second, the team undertook direct outreach to identify additional returnees and invite their participation, resulting in a further 79 interviews. In total, 164 returnees were interviewed between January and June 2025.

Given these constraints, the sampling strategy was non-probabilistic, and the findings should be interpreted as exploratory. The survey aimed to capture a range of return experiences in Tunisia rather than to produce nationally representative estimates. A key limitation is that, due to the relatively small non-probability sample, the results have limited generalisability to the wider returnee population. This also has implications for cross-country comparison within WP8, as variations in sampling strategies and sample composition may influence the patterns observed across countries.

Data were collected through face-to-face interviews using printed paper questionnaires. Completed questionnaires were coded manually, entered into Excel, and subsequently analysed in R. This workflow supported consistent data entry and enabled systematic quantitative analysis of return experiences across the selected study sites.

As in Afghanistan, the University of Sousse team in Tunisia encountered structural constraints in securing cooperation from both state and non-state actors for the field survey, including difficulties in reaching a sufficient number of female returnees. Research on migration also remained a sensitive area, where despite obtaining ethical clearance certificate, access-related challenges persisted, including heightened scrutiny by government officials during interactions with returnees and, in some instances, constraints on where and how interviews could be conducted.

3. Demographics

The proportion of male participants was high in all four country samples, with the most notable being in Tunisia, where only 2 of 164 respondents were female, followed by Iraq (46/250), Afghanistan (84/416), and the highest in Nigeria (125/288). (see Table 1). The gender imbalance in the survey samples reflects structural barriers to interviewing women returnees, such as limited mobility, gatekeeping by households (in case of Tunis and Iraq, Afghanistan) or authorities (in case of Afghanistan), and constraints on deploying female enumerators, like in Afghanistan. Methodologically, the imbalance reduces the precision of gender-disaggregated comparisons, particularly for Tunisia and Iraq, because the female sub-samples are small. These limitations should be acknowledged explicitly, as women's return trajectories, access to assistance, and reintegration challenges may differ from those of men.

Tunisia had a relatively young participant profile (mean age = 33.26, SD = 13.68) and, correspondingly, the highest proportion of single respondents (72.6%). Afghanistan showed a similarly young profile (mean age = 33.1, SD = 10.5); however, it recorded the highest proportion of married respondents among the partner countries (72.4%). In Nigeria, the mean age was 34.0 (SD = 8.74), and 38.89% of respondents were married. In Nigerian sample, marital status is also included the categories of separated (n= 4) and single mother (n=10).

Overall, the demographic profiles point to meaningful cross-country differences in both life-course stage and household structure. Here, the standard deviation (SD) indicates how widely respondents' ages vary around the average age: a higher SD means ages are more spread out, while a lower SD means ages are more clustered around the mean. Although Tunisia and Afghanistan have comparable mean ages (around 33 years), Tunisia exhibits substantially

greater age dispersion (SD = 13.68) than Afghanistan (SD = 10.5), suggesting a more heterogeneous sample that likely includes both younger and older returnees. Nigeria's mean age is slightly higher (34.0), and its lower SD (8.74) indicates a more tightly clustered age distribution.

Marital status patterns diverge sharply and may reflect differences in migration routes, selectivity, and return conditions. Tunisia's very high proportion of single respondents (72.6%) points to a returnee profile that is more individualised and potentially youth-dominated, consistent with mobility patterns in which unmarried individuals are more likely to undertake migration and be subject to return. By contrast, Afghanistan records the highest proportion of married respondents (72.4%), suggesting that return in this context may be more family-linked. Nigeria sits between these extremes, with a comparatively lower share of married respondents (38.89%), which may indicate a more mixed returnee composition or different reintegration strategies shaped by urban labour markets and social networks.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics: Age, Gender and Martial Status

Characteristics	Category/Statistics	Afghanistan		Iraq		Nigeria		Tunisia	
		n	%Value	n	%Value	n	%Value	n	%Value
Age	Mean Age in Years (SD)	416 ⁵	33.1 (10.5)	250	38.94 (11.94)	288	34 (8.74)	164	33.26 (13.68)
Gender	Male	332	79.8	204	81.6	163	56.6	162	98.78
	Female	84	20.2	46	18.4	125	43.4	2	1.22
Marital Status	Married	301	72.4	154	61.6	112	38.89	33	19.5
	Single	64	15.4	80	32	143	49.65	119	72.6
	Engaged	28	6.4	2	0.8	8	2.78	6	3.7
	Widowed/Divorced	23	5.5	14 ⁶	5.5	25 ⁷	8.68	7	4.3

4. Time and Country of Return

In Afghanistan, most respondents reported returning in 2023 (n = 223) and 2022 (n = 91), with a smaller number indicating return in 2024 (n = 11). This may reflect the pause in Pakistan's Illegal Foreigners Deportation Programme in 2024⁸. Earlier return years were

⁵ The number of participants was comparatively higher than in the other partner countries (n = 416), largely due to access to national statistics on return migrants obtained through the Memorandum of Understanding.

⁶ Divorced=10; Widowed=4

⁷ In Nigeria sample, marital Status includes the categories of Separated = 4; single mother=10.

⁸ Humanitarian Action: Analysing Need and Responses (2025), <https://humanitarianaction.info/document/global-humanitarian-overview-2025/article/afghanistan-rrp-1>

reported less frequently: 2021 (n = 17), 2020 (n = 35), 2019 (n = 18), 2018 (n = 6), 2017 (n = 9), and 2016 or earlier (n = 6).

In Tunisia, most respondents reported returning in 2024 (n = 56) and 2023 (n = 41), followed by limited numbers in 2022 (n = 16) and 2025 (n = 15). In Iraq, there is more fluctuations, returns were most commonly reported in 2024 (n = 54) and 2016 or earlier (n = 83), followed by numbers in some dozens in 2023 (n = 24), 2018 (n = 16), 2022 (n = 15), 2019 (n = 14), 2017 (n = 13), 2025 (n = 12), 2021 (n = 11), 2020 (n = 9), 2014 (n = 2), and only one in 2013. In Nigeria, most respondents in the sample reported returning in 2023 (n = 86) and 2022 (n = 56), with smaller numbers reporting return in 2018 (n = 37), 2024 (n = 28), 2019 (n = 25), 2020 (n = 20), 2017 (n = 8), and 2016 (n = 2) (see Table 2).

Table 2: Number of Return Per Year: 2016 - 2025

Year		2025	2024	2023	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018	2017	2016 & earlier	Sample Size
Number of Return by country	Afghanistan	-	11	223	91	17	35	18	6	9	6	416
	Iraq	12	54	24	15	11	9	14	16	13	83	250
	Nigeria	-	28	86	56	25	20	25	37	8	3	288
	Tunisia	15	56	41	16	11	6	4	2	1	12	164

5. The Route of Return

In Afghanistan, most respondents reported returning from Iran (n = 214), followed by Pakistan (n = 196), with a small number returning from Belgium (n = 2), Bulgaria (n = 2), and Malaysia (n = 1). It is also important to note that 106 of the 416 respondents reported spending time in a second country before returning to Afghanistan; in these cases, the most reported second countries were Türkiye (n = 67) and Pakistan (n = 31), followed by Saudi Arabia (n = 2) (see Table 3). In Iraq, the majority of respondents reported returning from Germany (n = 126), followed by Greece (n = 39), Sweden (n = 38), Finland (n = 30), Austria (n = 16), Belgium (n = 10), France (n = 8), the Netherlands (n = 6), Bulgaria (n = 5), Denmark (n = 3), and Switzerland (n = 3). Smaller numbers reported returning from Poland, the United Kingdom (UK), and Belarus (each n = 2), and from Norway, Italy, Romania, Ukraine, Hungary, Serbia, Lithuania, and Malta (each n = 1) (see Table 3).

In Nigeria, most respondents reported returning from Libya (n=85) followed by Germany (n=26), Sudan (n=23), and Niger (n=15). In Tunisia, the majority of respondents reported returning from Italy (n=75), followed by France (n=43), Germany (n=39), Switzerland (n=3), Austria, Brazil, Denmark and the Netherlands (each n=1). Like Afghanistan, a considerable number of respondents reported spending time in a second country before returning to Nigeria; in these cases, the most reported second countries were Niger (n=21), Mauritania (n=12), Togo (n=10), Senegal and Mali (each n=7) (see Table 3).

Table 3: Countries returned from to Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria and Tunisia

Countries returned to	Afghanistan		Iraq		Nigeria		Tunisia		
	Country	n	Country	n	Country	n	Country	n	
	Iran	214	Germany	126	Libya	85	Italy	75	
	Pakistan	196	Greece	39	Germany	26	France	43	
	Belgium	2	Sweden	38	Sudan	23	Germany	39	
	Bulgaria	2	Finland	30	Tunisia	16	Switzerland	3	
	Malaysia	1	Austria	16	Niger/Italy	Each n=15	Austria/Brazil/Denmark/Netherlands	Each n=1	
	Türkiye (2nd country) ⁹	67	Belgium	10	France	10			
	Pakistan (2nd country)	31	France	8	Spain/The Netherlands	Each n=9			
	Saudi Arabia	2	The Netherlands	6	Morocco/Oman/Switzerland	Each n=6			
India, Iraq, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan	Each n= 1	Bulgaria	5	Belgium/Denmark/Greece/Hungary/Ghana/Greece/Malta/Poland/Sweden/Togo	Each n=5				
		Denmark/Switzerland	Each n=3	Austria/Ireland	Each n=4				
		Poland/UK/Belarus Macedonia	Each n=2	Mali/Norway	Each n=3	Libya (second country)	87		
				Tunisia (second country)	21				
		Norway/Italy/Romania/Ukraine/Hungary/Serbia/Lithonia/Malta	Each n=1	Niger/Sudan (second country)	Each n=14	Morocco	10		
				Mauritania/Ghana	Each n=6				
Sample Size	416		250		288		164		

⁹ A considerable number of respondents reported spending time in a second country before returning to countries of origin, i.e. Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, Tunisia

6. Forced or Voluntary Return

In Afghanistan, 312 of 416 respondents (75%) reported being deported or forcibly returned from host countries, while the remaining 104 (25%) reported returning voluntarily. In Iraq, 44 of 250 respondents (17.6%) reported being deported or forcibly removed, while the remaining 206 (82.4%) reported returning voluntarily (for details see Chart 1).

In Nigeria, the out of 288 respondents 204 (70.83 %) reported being forcibly returned from host countries, while 84 (29.17%) returned voluntarily. In the case of Tunisia, out of 164 respondents 109 (66%) reported being deported or forcibly returned from host countries, while 55 (34%) reported returning voluntarily. Respondents from Iraq show differences than other cases, the percentage of voluntary return is higher than forced ones, for example 44 of 250 respondents (17.6%) reported being deported or forcibly removed, while the remaining 206 (82.4%) reported returning voluntarily (see Chart 1).

Chart 1: Forced or Voluntary Return

7. Detention Experiences Abroad

The detention profiles differ markedly across the four country samples, suggesting variation in enforcement practices, return pathways, and the contexts in which returns were carried out. Overall, Afghanistan and Iraq are characterised by relatively short detention episodes for most respondents, whereas Nigeria and Tunisia show more extended and more evenly distributed detention durations (see Table 5).

In Afghanistan, detention was most commonly short-term: the largest group reported being detained for less than two weeks ($n = 80$). Longer detention durations were reported less frequently, with relatively small numbers indicating detention beyond one month ($n = 21$ for more than one month but less than two months; $n = 25$ for more than two months but less than six months) and only a small minority reporting detention exceeding six months ($n = 9$).

(see Table 5). This pattern suggests that, for many Afghan returnees in the sample, detention functioned primarily as a brief holding period prior to removal centres, rather than prolonged imprisonment.

Iraq follows a similar, but even more concentrated, pattern of short detention. Most reported detention of less than two weeks ($n = 35$), and the frequency declines steadily as detention length increases ($n = 11$ for two weeks to one month; $n = 5$ for one to two months; $n = 9$ for two to six months; $n = 3$ for more than six months) (see Table 5). Compared to Afghanistan, the Iraqi sample reports fewer cases in every longer-duration category, indicating that extended detention was comparatively uncommon.

Nigeria presents a different profile, with a substantial share reporting longer detention. While short detention remains significant (less than two weeks: $n = 36$), notable numbers reported detention of two weeks to one month ($n = 30$) and one to two months ($n = 28$). Importantly, prolonged detention of more than six months is relatively high ($n = 21$), exceeding Afghanistan ($n = 9$) and Iraq ($n = 3$) (see Table 5). This distribution implies that, for many Nigerian returnees, detention was not merely a short administrative step but could involve extended periods of imprisonment prior to return.

Tunisia stands out for its unusually uniform distribution across categories after the shortest period. Although the largest group still reported detention of less than two weeks ($n = 26$), the remaining categories are evenly reported ($n = 21$) in each category from two weeks to one month, one to two months, two to six months, and more than six months (see Table 5). Interestingly, these findings indicate that Tunisia differs from the other cases in not exhibiting a sharp concentration in short-term detention alone.

Table 4: Detention Experience Aboard

Country	Time Spent in Detention	
	Time Spent	n
Afghanistan	Less than 2 weeks	80
	From 2 weeks to 1 month	24
	More than 1 month, less than 2 months	21
	More than 2 month, less than 6 months	25
	More than 6 months	9
Iraq	Less than 2 weeks	35
	From 2 weeks to 1 month	11
	More than 1 month, less than 2 months	5
	More than 2 month, less than 6 months	9
	More than 6 months	3
Nigeria	Less than 2 weeks	36
	From 2 weeks to 1 month	30
	More than 1 month, less than 2 months	28
	More than 2 month, less than 6 months	5
	More than 6 months	21
Tunisia	Less than 2 weeks	26
	From 2 weeks to 1 month	21
	More than 1 month, less than 2 months	21
	More than 2 month, less than 6 months	21
	More than 6 months	21

As shown in Table 4, the results indicate two broad clusters: Afghanistan and Iraq, where detention is predominantly short, and Nigeria and Tunisia, where a larger share of

respondents experienced medium- to long detention durations, including detention exceeding six months. These differences matter because detention duration can shape returnees' post-return outcomes. Extended detention may intensify economic depletion, psychosocial stress, and disruption of social ties, while shorter detention may reduce exposure to prolonged imprisonment but still signal coercive return conditions. At the same time, cross-country interpretation should remain cautious, as reported detention durations may also reflect differences in sampling sizes, legal regimes, and respondents' willingness or ability to report detention experiences.

8. Source of Financial Support for Return

In Afghanistan, return support, meaning who paid the cost of removal and arrival in the origin country was predominantly self- and network-financed: the most frequently reported sources were loans from family and friends (220 cases) and personal savings (194 cases). By comparison, assistance from international organisations was less common, with IOM (83 cases) and UNHCR (48 cases) based financial assistance cited at lower levels, alongside smaller numbers reporting gifts from family/friends (37 cases) and asset sales (15 cases). This pattern suggests that many Afghan returnees relied heavily on informal social networks and private coping strategies rather than formal assistance mechanisms (see Table 4).

Iraq shows a more mixed profile with a stronger role for host-country support. Host countries were the most frequently reported source (95 cases), followed by IOM (60 cases) and savings (51 cases), while loans from family/friends were also common (49 cases). UNHCR (21 cases) and INGOs/NGOs (16 cases) appeared less frequently, and other government support was reported only sporadically (see Table 4). Overall, the Iraqi distribution points to a greater institutional footprint in return support, particularly from host countries and IOM, relative to Afghanistan, while still indicating considerable reliance on savings and family networks.

Nigeria displays the clearest institutionalised return-support pattern among the four cases. IOM (121 cases) and EU countries (111 cases) dominate reported sources, whereas private resources such as savings (12 cases) and family/friend support (4 cases) appear comparatively limited (see Table 4). This suggests that a substantial share of surveyed Nigerian returnees returned through assisted return channels, where costs are more likely to be covered by formal programmes linked to European partners and implementing agencies.

Tunisia, by contrast, is dominated by a broad "other" category (80 cases), followed by savings (43 cases), with relatively limited reporting of formal organisational support (IOM 16 cases; UNHCR 5 cases) and modest reliance on family/friend support (13 cases) (see Table 4). This distribution may reflect heterogeneity in return pathways and reporting categories, as well as the absence of a single dominant institutional channel comparable to Nigeria's IOM/EU pattern. At the same time, the prominence of savings indicates that, for many Tunisian returnees in the sample, the return was privately financed.

Comparatively, the data suggest (see Table 4) a continuum from primarily informal financing (Afghanistan) to mixed arrangements with notable host-country and IOM involvement (Iraq), to strongly programme-assisted return (Nigeria), and finally to a more heterogeneous configuration in Tunisia where "other" (i.e., French government, Italian government, German government and other charity organisations) and savings are most prominent. These differences have implications for reintegration, as returnees who self-finance through debt or asset sales may re-enter with depleted resources and higher vulnerability, whereas those returning through assisted channels may have better initial coverage of emergency needs, short-term support, though this does not necessarily translate into longer-term reintegration outcomes.

Table 5: Source of Financial Support for Return

Country	Afghanistan		Iraq		Nigeria		Tunisia	
	Source	Frequency	Source	Frequency	Source	Frequency	Source	Frequency
Sources Support Return	Loan from Family & Friends	220	Host Countries	95	IOM	121	Others (French government, Italian government, German government, and other charity organisations)	80
	Saving	194	Saving	51	EU Countries	111	Saving	43
	IOM	83	Loan from Family Friends	49	Government of African Countries	22	IOM	16
	UNHCR	48	IOM	60	Saving	12	Gift/support from Family and Friends	13
	Gift from Family & Friend	37	UNHCR	21	UNHCR	7	UNHCR	5
	Sales of property	15	INGOs/NGOs	16	Other	5	Employer/business	4
	Loan	2	Other Governments	8	Support from Family and Friend	4		
			Government of Iraq	1				

9. Likelihood of Legal or Illegal Migration

One of the interview questions is about the re-migration intention of returnees. For legal re-migration aspirations, returnee respondents from Tunisia (62.8% likely; n = 103) and Iraq (60.8% likely; n = 152) report the highest levels of likelihood, suggesting that a majority of respondents in these samples are open to pursuing legal onward mobility. By contrast, Afghanistan shows markedly lower reported likelihood of legal re-migration (23% likely; n = 96), with the large majority indicating unlikelihood (77%; n = 320). This points to a more limited expressed intention to legally re-migrate among Afghan returnees compared to Iraq and Tunisia. This might be attributed lacking almost any chance for legal migration pathways.

For illegal re-migration, the dominant pattern is unlikely in all countries, but the magnitude differs. Afghanistan shows the strongest rejection of irregular re-migration (15% likely; n = 62 versus 85% unlikely; n = 354), followed by Iraq (21.2% likely; n = 53 versus 76.8% unlikely; n = 192). Tunisia stands out with the highest proportion reporting a likelihood of illegal re-migration (34.75% likely; n = 57), although the majority still report being unlikely (58.53%; n = 96). Overall, the Tunisian sample appears comparatively more open to irregular re-migration than the Afghan and Iraqi samples.

Table 6: Likelihood of Legal and Illegal Migration

Country	Sample Size	Legal Re-Migration		Illegal Re-Migration	
		Likely	Unlikely	Likely	Unlikely
Afghanistan ¹¹	416	n=96 (23%)	n= 320 (77%)	n=62 (15%)	n=354 (85%)
Iraq ¹²	250	n=152 (60.8%)	n=87 (34.8%)	n=53 (21.2%)	n=192 (76.8%)
Nigeria	288	n = 179 (62.2%)	n = 48 (16.7%)	n = 53 (18.4%)	n = 168 (58.3%)
Tunisia ¹³	164	n=103 (62.80%)	n=45 (27.43%)	n=57 (34.75%)	n=96 (58.53%)

¹⁰ For response options ranging from 1 = very unlikely to 5 = very likely, “somewhat likely” and “very likely” are interpreted as indicating a likelihood and “somewhat unlikely” and “very unlikely” indicating unlikelihood of re-migration.

¹¹ Only 1% of respondents indicated “neither likely nor unlikely” for legal and irregular migration.

¹² 11 respondents (4.4% of total respondents) in Iraq indicated “neither likely nor unlikely” for legal migration and only 5 respondents (2% of total respondents) in Iraq indicated “neither likely nor unlikely” for illegal migration.

¹³ 15 respondents (9.14% of total respondents) in Iraq indicated “neither likely nor unlikely” for legal migration and only 10 respondents (6% of total respondents) in Iraq indicated “neither likely nor unlikely” for illegal migration.

10. Hope and Resilience

10.1 Hope

The concept of hope is a crucial psychological, social, and moral resource for migrants, functioning as a key driver of resilience and a way to make sense of extreme adversity (Eggerman & Panter-Brick, 2010). For returnees confronting “broken economies”, social marginalisation, or political violence, hope counters feelings of entrapment (Eggerman & Panter-Brick, 2010). Hope is not merely the conviction that things will improve, but that life remains meaningful even when outcomes are uncertain (Eggerman & Panter-Brick, 2010). It offers a narrative framework that helps people interpret suffering while preserving dignity. Psychologically, hope is understood as a “cognitive set”, involving both the belief in one’s capacity to act and the ability to generate pathways toward meaningful goals (Snyder et al., 1996).

The Dispositional Hope Scale, a 12-item instrument developed by Snyder et al. (1991), was used to measure respondents’ levels of hope across the four study countries (Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, and Tunisia). The instrument of hope is a self-report measure of a cognitive set comprising two interrelated, reciprocally derived components: agency and pathways (Snyder et al., 1996). The scale captures key dimensions of hope, including optimism about life, goal-directed thinking and motivation to pursue goals, and the extent to which respondents feel confident—or concerned, about achieving desired outcomes. The participants rate items on an 8-point continuum ranging from 1 (definitely false) to 8 (definitely true).

The descriptive statistics indicate broadly comparable—though not identical—levels of hope across the four country samples. Mean hope scores range from 3.30 to 3.62, suggesting that respondents in all settings reported moderate to relatively high hope on the scale used. Tunisia recorded the highest average hope ($M = 3.62$, $SD = 0.57$), followed closely by Nigeria ($M = 3.56$, $SD = 0.56$) and Iraq ($M = 3.53$, $SD = 0.47$). Afghanistan reported the lowest mean ($M = 3.30$, $SD = 0.57$), indicating comparatively lower levels of hope among respondents in that sample.

In terms of dispersion, the standard deviations are relatively similar across countries (0.47–0.57), implying broadly comparable within-country variability in hope (see Table 7). Iraq shows the lowest SD (0.47), suggesting that respondents’ hope scores are more tightly clustered around the mean (i.e., more homogeneous perceptions of hope). By contrast, Afghanistan and Tunisia ($SD = 0.57$) and Nigeria ($SD = 0.56$) display slightly greater variability, indicating more heterogeneity in hope levels within those samples (see Table 7).

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics for Hope Scale by Country (Mean, SD)

Country	Afghanistan	Iraq	Nigeria	Tunisia
Descriptive statistics	3.30 (SD=0.57)	3.53 (SD=0.47)	3.56 (SD=0.56)	3.62 (SD=0.57)
Mean, SD				

10.2 Resilience

Resilience research is crucial in migration studies because it shifts attention from deficit-focused perspectives to the culturally grounded ways individuals and communities adapt to

high-risk environments (Eggerman & Panter-Brick, 2010; Aranda et al., 2012). Earlier research often emphasised risk, trauma, and pathology while overlooking the cultural values that sustain migrants' capacity to endure adversity (Eggerman & Panter-Brick, 2010). Migration itself is a multi-layered process shaped by interacting biological, psychological, social, and ecological systems (Ungar, 2021). A resilience lens helps explain how these levels influence one another; for example, how a broken economy can contribute to psychological distress at the individual level (Eggerman & Panter-Brick, 2010). Understanding these broader dynamics is essential for designing sustainable, long-term reintegration and support strategies (Ungar, 2021).

A 10-item version of the Connor–Davidson Resilience Scale (Connor and Davidson, 2003) was used to assess respondents' resilience, understood as their perceived capacity to cope with stress, adapt to adversity, and recover from psychosocial pressures.

The descriptive statistics suggest that respondents across all four countries report moderate to relatively high levels of resilience, with mean scores ranging from 3.57 to 3.96. Tunisia records the highest mean resilience score ($M = 3.96$, $SD = 0.78$), indicating that respondents in the Tunisian sample, on average, report the strongest perceived capacity to cope with psychosocial pressures (see Table 8). Iraq follows ($M = 3.76$, $SD = 0.61$), while Nigeria reports a slightly lower mean ($M = 3.69$, $SD = 0.80$). Afghanistan has the lowest average resilience score ($M = 3.57$, $SD = 0.74$) among the four samples (see Table 8).

In terms of variability, Iraq shows the lowest SD (0.61), suggesting that resilience scores are more tightly clustered and relatively more homogeneous within that sample. Nigeria has the highest SD (0.80), indicating greater variability and divergency—i.e., resilience levels vary more widely among Nigerian respondents. Tunisia ($SD = 0.78$) and Afghanistan ($SD = 0.74$) also show substantial within-sample variation, implying that while average resilience is relatively high, especially in Tunisia, respondents' experiences and coping capacities differ notably within these contexts (see Table 8).

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Resilience Scale by Country (Mean, SD)

Country	Afghanistan	Iraq	Nigeria	Tunisia
Descriptive statistics	3.57 (SD=0.74)	3.76 (SD=0.61)	3.69 (SD=0.80)	3.96 (SD=0.78)
Mean, SD				

11. Discussion and Recommendations

Overall, the comparative findings indicate that post-return practices and reintegration experiences vary across Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, and Tunisia, yet they are shaped by a set of recurring structural constraints. Across the four cases, return and reintegration systems remain fragmented and insufficiently comprehensive, often failing to provide coordinated support that addresses returnees' short-, medium-, and long-term needs. This institutional gap is particularly consequential in contexts where return is predominantly involuntary. In three of the four settings, the share of deported or forcibly returned respondents was very high—Afghanistan (75%), Nigeria (70.83%), and Tunisia (66%)—suggesting that many returnees re-entered their countries of origin under conditions likely to exacerbate vulnerability and disrupt preparation for reintegration. Iraq constitutes a notable outlier, with a substantially lower proportion of forced return (17.6%), pointing to different return dynamics and governance conditions. Several factors such as failure to secure residence permit in the host country, feeling of marginalisation, sense of belonging and attachment to the home country, and responsibility to care for family members back home were key drivers shaping Iraqi migrants' decisions to return.

The report further highlights that public, government-led financial assistance for returnees is limited across countries, reinforcing the broader pattern of weak institutional support. In Iraq, for instance, only one respondent reported receiving financial support from the Iraqi government. Taken together, these results underscore a central implication for return governance: in the absence of predictable, coordinated, and adequately resourced reintegration programming, particularly in contexts of large-scale forced return, returnees are more likely to rely on informal coping mechanisms and face uneven reintegration trajectories shaped by household resources, social networks, and local reception conditions. For example, substantial numbers of returnees across the four countries relied on savings (Afghanistan: n = 194; Iraq: n = 51; Tunisia: n = 43; Nigeria: n = 12), as well as on coping strategies such as selling property, taking loans, and receiving support from family and friends (Afghanistan: n = 220; Iraq: n = 49) to finance their return.

Despite the fact that many returnees across the four countries reported having experienced detention and/or forcible return from host countries, a substantial share still viewed re-migration, through both legal and, in some cases, irregular pathways, as a key coping strategy in response to the adversities they face in their countries of origin. This suggests that return is often not experienced as a durable solution; rather, for some respondents, onward mobility remains an active component of household survival strategies and future planning in contexts of continued insecurity, limited livelihoods, and weak reintegration support.

Returnees' resilience practices diverged in response to differing levels of adversities, contextual conditions and return and reintegration arrangements. Among the four countries, Afghanistan recorded the lowest resilience score, an outcome that may aligns with a context in which many returnees were largely left to cope on their own, with limited government assistance and comparatively constrained international support.

Afghanistan's lower resilience scores are accompanied by the lowest hope levels among the four countries, suggesting that constrained support environments may depress both forward-looking expectations and coping capacity. Limited assistance, unstable livelihoods, poor access to essential services, a weak protection environment, and reduced opportunities for re-migration, especially due to increasingly restrictive visa policies affecting Afghans in many countries, including Pakistan and Iran (which host the largest Afghan populations),

simultaneously diminish optimism about the future (hope) and erode coping capacity (resilience).

Recommendations

- Establish a coordinated institutional mechanism to manage return and reintegration across the full cycle (arrival, immediate assistance, and longer-term reintegration)

It should explicitly cover short-term needs (registration, shelter, food, documentation, urgent health and protection), medium-term needs (cash/livelihood start-up, debt management for those who finance return through savings/loans, psychosocial support), and long-term needs (employment pathways, housing/land access, education, and psychosocial inclusion). This is particularly important in Afghanistan, Iraq, and Tunisia. In Nigeria, by contrast, long-term, community-led psychosocial and economic support is crucial to strengthen psychosocial resilience and reduce stigma.

- Promote voluntary return and strengthen pre-return cooperation so that return is planned, rights-based, and linked to reintegration capacity in countries of origin.

The high proportions of deportation/forcible return and the reported detention experiences in Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria and Tunisia indicate that return often occurs under constrained conditions. Pre-return cooperation should include:

- Timely information-sharing on return caseloads and profiles. For example, in the Case of Nigeria, partners in host countries must communicate and coordinate with NCFRMI to determine and plan return locations.
- Pre-departure counselling and documentation support,
- Agreements that link return operations to realistic reintegration options in countries of origin (including referrals to services on arrival).
- Develop joint operational–research platforms within countries of origin to improve coordination between state and non-state stakeholders and reduce duplication.
- A joint platform (government agencies, local authorities, UN agencies, NGOs/CSOs, and community actors) should coordinate case management, harmonise eligibility criteria, and align assistance packages so that returnees do not face fragmented or inconsistent support across regions and programmes.
- Establish robust data-sharing mechanisms and support policy-oriented research by enabling ethical, secure access to administrative and programme data.

A standardised, GDPR-aligned data governance framework should support:

- Secure sharing of anonymised returnee registries and programme databases,
- Common variable definitions and reporting templates (e.g. detention duration, voluntariness of return, support received), and
- Predictable procedures for facilitating field research (ethical approvals, permissions, and safe access).
- Findings from Iraq, Nigeria and Tunisia indicate that state and non-state organisations conducting research, particularly doing field surveys and developing reports, would benefit

from capacity development training in data collection, interview ethics, data management, analysis and report writing.

References

- Aranda, K., Zeeman, L., Scholes, J., & Santa-María Morales, A. (2012). The resilient subject: Exploring subjectivity, identity and the body in narratives of resilience. *Health*, 16(5), 548–563. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1363459312438564>
- Displacement Tracking Matrix, (2019). ‘Iraqi Returnees From Abroad – Dashboard.’ [Online] Available at: <https://iraqdtm.iom.int>. Accessed: [September 02, 2025].
- Displacement Tracking Matrix, (2020). ‘Iraqi Returnees From Abroad – Dashboard.’ [Online] Available at: <https://iraqdtm.iom.int>. Accessed: [September 03, 2025].
- Eggerman, M., & Panter-Brick, C. (2010). Suffering, hope, and entrapment. *Social Science & Medicine*, 71(1), 71–83.
- IOM. (2025, April 30). *Government of Nigeria validates the 2025 National Migration Policy*. IOM, UN Migration. <https://nigeria.iom.int/news/government-nigeria-validates-2025-national-migration-policy>
- IOM (2025). ‘IOM Integrated Appeal for Afghan Returnees from Pakistan and Iran.’ Available at: <https://afghanistan.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd11071/files/documents/2024-06/iom-afghanistan-border-and-aor-appeal-2024.pdf> (Accessed: [insert date]).
- Michael, Y. (2023, May 6). ‘Nigerians left in Sudan will be evacuated soon, says NiDCOM.’ *TheCable*. <https://www.thecable.ng/nigerians-left-in-sudan-will-be-evacuated-soon-says-nidcom/>
- NATIP Act (2003) /<https://lawsofnigeria.placng.org/laws/T23.pdf>
- Snyder, C. R., Sympson, S. C., Ybasco, F. C., Borders, T. F., Babyak, M. A., & Higgins, R. L. (1996). Development and validation of the state hope scale. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 70(2), 321–335.
- Udu, E., Uwadiogwu, A. & Eseni, J. (2023). ‘Evaluating the Enforcement of the Rights of Women under the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) 1979: The Nigerian Experience.’ *Beijing Law Review*, 14, 764-782. doi: 10.4236/blr.2023.142041.
- Ungar, M. (Ed.). (2021). Modeling multisystemic resilience. In *Multisystemic resilience*. Oxford University Press.
- United Nations (2016, January 11). Combined seventh and eighth periodic reports submitted by Nigeria under article 18 of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women. CEDAW/C/NGA/7-8. <https://docs.un.org/en/CEDAW/C/NGA/7-8#:~:text=2.1%20Previous%20reports%20made%20it,of%20birth%20against%20any%20citizen.>
- United Nations (2025). *Iraq unveils historic migration plan to boost development and stability*. [Online] Available at: <https://news.un.org>. Accessed: [September 02, 2025].
- UNHCR (2024). ‘Italy Sea Arrivals Dashboard. December 2023’. Available at <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/107239>
- UNHCR (2025). ‘Afghanistan Situation: Afghan Returns Emergency Update #12.’ Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/118971> (Accessed: [insert date]).

Uzomah, N. L., & Madu, I. A. (2025). 'Reassessing Return Migration Governance: Insights on Nigeria's Return Migration Infrastructures.' WP3 Country Dossier" in *GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working paper 2025/13*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15222377

Appendix 1: Hope and Resilience Scales Afghanistan Case Study

This appendix included interview questions and documents the Hope and Resilience measures used in the WP8 survey instrument, including item wording, response formats, scoring procedures, and reliability information. The scales were administered to returnees as part of the structured questionnaire.

Screening Questions				
1		Did you return to Afghanistan in the past ten years? (If the respondent has returned multiple times, take into consideration the last time the respondent returned to the country)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> I don't Know	
2		Which country was your destination for which you emigrated from Afghanistan?	<i>Enter Country name</i>	
3		From which country did you return to Afghanistan?	<i>Enter Country name</i>	
4		Did you return to Afghanistan from Iran, Pakistan, Turkey, or EU countries? (If returned multiple times, the latest return is under consideration)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> I don't Know	
Section I: Demography				
No.	Question ID	Question	Response Option	Logic
1	DemoQ1.a	Age (years)		
2	DemoQ3.g	Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female	
3	DemoQ4.pr	Province (Residing Currently)		
4	DemoQ5.ds	District (Residing Currently)		
5	DemoQ6.vi	Village or Nahia (Residing Currently)		
6	DemoQ7.m s	Marital Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Single <input type="checkbox"/> Engaged <input type="checkbox"/> Married <input type="checkbox"/> Widow/widower <input type="checkbox"/> Divorced <input type="checkbox"/> Other	
7	DemoQ8.et	Ethnicity	<input type="checkbox"/> Pashtun <input type="checkbox"/> Tajik <input type="checkbox"/> Hazara <input type="checkbox"/> Uzbek <input type="checkbox"/> Aimaq <input type="checkbox"/> Baluch <input type="checkbox"/> Nooristani <input type="checkbox"/> Turkmen <input type="checkbox"/> Arab <input type="checkbox"/> Other	

8	DemoQ9.ql	What is the highest level of education you have achieved?	<input type="checkbox"/> Level 0: Early childhood education (01 Early childhood educational development) <input type="checkbox"/> Level 0: Early childhood education (02 Pre-primary education) <input type="checkbox"/> Level 1: Primary education <input type="checkbox"/> Level 2: Lower secondary education <input type="checkbox"/> Level 3: Upper secondary education <input type="checkbox"/> Level 4: Post-secondary non-tertiary education <input type="checkbox"/> Level 5: Short-cycle tertiary education <input type="checkbox"/> Level 6: Bachelor's or equivalent <input type="checkbox"/> Level 7: Master's or equivalent <input type="checkbox"/> Level 8: Doctorate or equivalent <input type="checkbox"/> Other, Specify -----
9	DemoQ10.hs	What is your household size? (Indicate number of members regularly living under the same roof, sharing meals and some resources)	
10	DemoQ11.em	Employment	<input type="checkbox"/> Managers <input type="checkbox"/> Professional <input type="checkbox"/> Technicians and associate professionals <input type="checkbox"/> Clerical support workers <input type="checkbox"/> Service and sales workers <input type="checkbox"/> Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers <input type="checkbox"/> Craft related trades workers <input type="checkbox"/> Plant and machine operators, and assemblers <input type="checkbox"/> Elementary occupations (cleaner/labourer) <input type="checkbox"/> Armed forces occupations <input type="checkbox"/> Unemployed <input type="checkbox"/> Other
11	DemoQ12.bz	Do you have any business links in region (i.e., Iran, Pakistan, Turkey, EU or other neighboring/regional countries)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
12	DemoQ13.in	What is your average monthly household income? (In AFN)	<input type="checkbox"/> No Income <input type="checkbox"/> Less than 5,000 <input type="checkbox"/> 5,000 – 10,000 <input type="checkbox"/> 11,000 – 15,000 <input type="checkbox"/> 16,000 – 20,000 <input type="checkbox"/> 21,000 – 25,000

			<input type="checkbox"/> 26,000 – 30,000 <input type="checkbox"/> 31,000 – 35,000 <input type="checkbox"/> 36,000 – 40,000 <input type="checkbox"/> 41,000 – 45,000 <input type="checkbox"/> 46,000 – 50,000 <input type="checkbox"/> 50,000 AFS +	
13	DemoQ14.md	Do you have any male children [aged 6-18] that are dependent on you?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
14	DemoQ15.f	Do you have any female children [aged 6-18] that are dependent on you?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
[MigQ11dt] Immigration Detention				
[MigQ11dt1]	Have you been detained for migration related reasons (not criminal related reasons) during your time outside your home country?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't Know	
[MigQ11dt2]	If you have been detained, how long were you detained for immigration related purposes?		<input type="checkbox"/> Less than 2 Weeks <input type="checkbox"/> Between 2 weeks and 1 Month <input type="checkbox"/> Greater than 1 Month and less than 2 Months <input type="checkbox"/> Greater than 2 Months and Less than 6 Months <input type="checkbox"/> Greater than 6 Months	
[MigQ11dt3]	If you have been detained, were there any of instances of detention related to return/deportation procedures?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't Know	

Section II: Migration

[MigQ1.c] In which countries have you travelled/ lived over the past 10 years?

No.	Countries	Year	Duration (In months)
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			
8			
9			
10			

[MigQ2.lm] Given your current situation, what likelihood is there for you to legally migrate to another country?

Note to the enumerator: Further expand on what is meant by legal migration. Legal migration can happen with a valid visa, residence permit, passport and others.

- 5 = Very likely
 4 = Somewhat likely
 3= Neither likely nor unlikely (somewhere in the middle)
 2 = Somewhat unlikely
 1 = Very unlikely

[[MigQ3.ilm] Given your current situation, what likelihood is there for you to illegally migrate to another country?

- 5 = Very likely
 4 = Somewhat likely
 3= Neither likely nor unlikely (somewhere in the middle)
 2 = Somewhat unlikely
 1 = Very unlikely

[MigQ4.rtd] In which month and year did you return to Afghanistan? (If you have returned multiple times, please list the date of your most recent return only.)

Month

Year

[MigQ5.rtd] We would like to understand your motivations for your return to Afghanistan.

Please provide us with your level of agreement with the following possible reasons for your return....

No.	Statements	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
MigQ5.rtd1	Poor security conditions in the host country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.rtd2	Poor economic conditions in the host country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.rtd3	Unemployment in host country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.rtd4	Family reunification in Afghanistan	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.rtd5	Could not get visa/permanent residency in host country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.rtd6	Deported/forcibly removed from host country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.rtd7	People of the host country were unwelcoming or discriminating toward you	<input type="checkbox"/>				

MigQ5.r td8	Security situation in Afghanistan improved	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.r td9	Economic conditions in Afghanistan improved	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.r td10	People are being treated well in Afghanistan	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.r td11	Arbitrary Detention in transit and destination country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.r td13	I love my country (Patriotism)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.r td14	Because of natural disasters in the host country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.r td15	Refugees are being forcibly taken to war in the host country	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.r td16	Because education has returned to Afghanistan	<input type="checkbox"/>				
MigQ5.r td17	Other (Specify)					
MigQ5.r td18	Don't Know					
MigQ5.r td19	Refused to Answer					

[MigQ6.sp] When you travelled back to Afghanistan for your return, how much money in total did you receive as part of Assisted Voluntary Return program?

[MigQ6.sp1]	UNHCR	Amount in AFN
[MigQ6.sp2]	IOM	Amount in AFN
[MigQ6.sp.3]	EU countries	
[MigQ6.sp.4]	Government of Turkiye	
[MigQ6.sp.5]	Government of Pakistan	
[MigQ6.sp.6]	Government of Iran	
[MigQ6.sp.7]	Government of Afghanistan	
[MigQ6.sp.8]	Other INGO or NGO (specify)	
[MigQ6.sp.9]	None	

[MigQ7.fin] How did you finance your trip back to Afghanistan? (DO NOT READ OUT)

[MigQ7.fin1]	<input type="checkbox"/> Savings
[MigQ7.fin2]	<input type="checkbox"/> Loan from family or friends
[MigQ7.fin3]	<input type="checkbox"/> Gift/support from family or friends
[MigQ7.fin4]	<input type="checkbox"/> Sell property
[MigQ7.fin5]	<input type="checkbox"/> Support from UNHCR
[MigQ7.fin6]	<input type="checkbox"/> Support from IOM
[MigQ7.fin7]	<input type="checkbox"/> Paid for by employer or business
[MigQ7.fin8]	<input type="checkbox"/> Loan from bank, broker, or other institution
[MigQ7.fin9]	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (Specify)

Embeddedness	
Social Embeddedness	
How many close friends do you have in your current community?	<input type="checkbox"/> Specify number
In case of hardship or any matter requiring immediate attention, who would be first to contact? (Multiple choice)	<input type="checkbox"/> Family <input type="checkbox"/> Friends <input type="checkbox"/> Relatives <input type="checkbox"/> Work colleagues <input type="checkbox"/> Neighbor <input type="checkbox"/> No one <input type="checkbox"/> Other
In the past two month, how many times have you attended the following events in your community? (Specify number).	<input type="checkbox"/> Social gathering (Mehmani) <input type="checkbox"/> Birthday party <input type="checkbox"/> Marriage (including wedding, engagement) <input type="checkbox"/> Funeral (Jinaza) <input type="checkbox"/> Khatem (Jomagi, Chel, funeral days) <input type="checkbox"/> Jirga <input type="checkbox"/> Travel for sightseeing (Chakar) <input type="checkbox"/> Other
How often do you apply the socio-cultural skills learned in the host country in your daily professional interactions in your home country?	<input type="checkbox"/> Rarely or never <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Frequently <input type="checkbox"/> Very frequently <input type="checkbox"/> Always
Have the socio-cultural skills learned in the host country improved your ability to adapt to different cultural contexts within your home country?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Slightly <input type="checkbox"/> Moderately <input type="checkbox"/> Significantly <input type="checkbox"/> Extremely

Economic Embeddedness	
Are you currently employed or engaged in income-generating activities since your return?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
What is the status of the house you live in?	<input type="checkbox"/> Rental <input type="checkbox"/> Lease (Graw) <input type="checkbox"/> Purchased and owned <input type="checkbox"/> Bank loan

How would you describe your current income compared to your income before you left your home country?	<input type="checkbox"/> Increased <input type="checkbox"/> About the same <input type="checkbox"/> Decreased
Have you started a business or entrepreneurial venture in your home country since your return?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
How satisfied are you with the performance and profitability of your business/venture (if any)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very dissatisfied
Are you able to meet your basic financial needs (e.g., housing, food, healthcare) without difficulty?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, totally <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> A little <input type="checkbox"/> Not really <input type="checkbox"/> No, not at all
Are the skills you acquired abroad relevant to the job or work you are currently doing in your home country?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, very relevant <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat relevant <input type="checkbox"/> A little relevant <input type="checkbox"/> Not really relevant <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant at all
To what extent do you believe the skills acquired in the host country have enhanced your employability prospects in Afghanistan?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Slightly <input type="checkbox"/> Moderately <input type="checkbox"/> Significantly <input type="checkbox"/> Extremely
Have you been able to secure loans or access credit for business or personal purposes in your home country?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I have <input type="checkbox"/> No I have not

[MigQ12Lm] Rate how much each of the following gives your life meaning now.					
	Family	Friends	Religion/ Spirituality	Work/ School	Other (specify)
Helps very much	10 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	9 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	8 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	7 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	6 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	5 <input type="checkbox"/>				

	4 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	3 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	2 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	1 <input type="checkbox"/>				
Doesn't help at all	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>
Not relevant	NA <input type="checkbox"/>				

[MigQ13CDf] Rate how much each of the following helps you handle any difficult situation you are facing.					
	Family	Friends	Religion/ Spirituality	Work/ School	Other (specify)
Helps very much	10 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	9 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	8 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	7 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	6 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	5 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	4 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	3 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	2 <input type="checkbox"/>				
	1 <input type="checkbox"/>				
Doesn't help at all	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>
Not relevant	NA <input type="checkbox"/>				

Section V: Health

[HealthQ1] In general, would you say your health is:

- 5 = Excellent
- 4 = Very good
- 3 = Good
- 2 = Somewhat Good
- 1 = Bad

Depression Scale

No.	Statements	Rarely or none of the time (less than 1 day)	Some or a little of the time (1-2 days)	Occasionally or a moderate amount of time (3-4 days)	All of the time (5-7 days)

DepressionQ2a	I was bothered by things that usually don't bother me.				
DepressionQ2b	I had trouble keeping my mind on what I was doing				
DepressionQ2c	I felt depressed				
DepressionQ2d	I feel that everything I do is an effort to remain alive.				
DepressionQ2e	I am optimistic and hopeful about the future.				
DepressionQ2f	I felt fearful.				
DepressionQ2g	My sleep was restless				
DepressionQ2h	I was happy				
DepressionQ2i	I felt lonely.				
DepressionQ2j	I could not "get going."				
DepressionQ2k	I was bothered by things that usually don't bother me.				
DepressionQ2l	I had trouble keeping my mind on what I was doing				

A. Hope Scale (12 items)

Purpose: The Hope Scale measures goal-directed thinking, capturing both perceived pathways to goals and agency (motivation to pursue goals).

Response options (5-point Likert scale).

1 = Strongly disagree

2 = Disagree

3 = Neither agree nor disagree

4 = Agree

5 = Strongly agree

Items. Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which each statement describes them.

Code	Item wording	Reverse-coded
HopeQ1a	I can think of many ways to get out of a jam.	No
HopeQ1b	I energetically pursue my goals.	No
HopeQ1c	I feel tired most of the time.	Yes
HopeQ1d	There are lots of ways around any problem.	No
HopeQ1e	I am easily downed in an argument.	Yes
HopeQ1f	I can think of many ways to get the things in life that are important to me.	No
HopeQ1g	I worry about my health.	Yes
HopeQ1h	Even when others get discouraged, I know I can find a way to solve the problem.	No
HopeQ1i	My past experiences have prepared me well for my future.	No
HopeQ1j	I've been pretty successful in life.	No
HopeQ1k	I usually find myself worrying about something.	Yes
HopeQ1l	I meet the goals that I set for myself.	No

Scoring procedure.

1. Reverse-code negatively worded items: HopeQ1c, HopeQ1e, HopeQ1g, HopeQ1k.
 - Reverse-coding rule (1–5 scale): Reversed score = 6 – original score.
2. Compute the Hope total score as the sum of all 12 items after reverse-coding.
 - Range: 12–60 (higher scores indicate higher hope).
3. If required for reporting comparability, compute the Hope mean score as: total score ÷ 12 (range 1.00–5.00).

Reliability (Pilot¹⁴). Cronbach's alpha indicated acceptable internal consistency for the Hope Scale in the pilot - scale source (Snyder et al. 1991).

B. Resilience Scale (10 items)

Purpose: The Resilience Scale measures perceived adaptive capacity and the ability to cope with stress and adversity.

Response options (5-point Likert scale).

1 = Not true at all

2 = Rarely true

3 = Sometimes true

¹⁴ Conducted in December 2023, a total of 98 respondent participated in Pilot survey.

4 = Often true

5 = True nearly all the time

Items: Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which each statement describes them.

Code	Item wording	Reverse-coded
ResilQ1a	I am able to adapt when changes occur.	No
ResilQ1b	I can deal with whatever comes my way.	No
ResilQ1c	I try to see the humorous side of things when I am faced with problems.	No
ResilQ1d	Having to cope with stress can make me stronger.	No
ResilQ1e	I tend to bounce back after illness, injury or other hardships.	No
ResilQ1f	I believe I can achieve my goals, even if there are obstacles.	No
ResilQ1g	Under pressure, I stay focused and think clearly.	No
ResilQ1h	I am not easily discouraged by failure.	No
ResilQ1i	I think of myself as a strong person when dealing with life's challenges and difficulties.	No
ResilQ1j	I am able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear, and anger.	No

Scoring procedure.

1. No reverse-coded items are applied for the Resilience Scale as implemented in the WP8 instrument.
2. Compute the **Resilience total score** as the **sum** of the 10 items.
 - o **Range:** 10–50 (higher scores indicate higher resilience).
3. If required for reporting comparability, compute the **Resilience mean score** as: total score ÷ 10 (range 1.00–5.00).

Reliability (Pilot ¹⁵). Cronbach's alpha indicated strong internal consistency for the Resilience Scale in the pilot.

Scale source. Adapted from Connor and Davidson (2003)

¹⁵ Conducted in December 2023, a total of 98 respondent participated in Pilot survey.

About the Authors

Hidayet Siddıkođlu, PhD, Director of Bilim Organisation, Afghanistan

Andreas Önver Cetrez, Professor at Uppsala University

Copyright Clause

This work is licensed by the GAPs Consortium under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License, 2020. For details, see <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

The GAPs Consortium

Uppsala University (Sweden, Co-Coordinator)
Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (Germany, Co-Coordinator)
Stichting Radboud Universiteit (Netherlands)
Ozyegin Universitesi (Turkey)
Hammurabi Human Rights Organization (Iraq)
Svenska Forskningsinstitutet i Istanbul (Sweden/Turkey)
Hashemite University (Jordan)
National Centre for Social Research (EKKE) (Greece)
Association Migration Internationale (Morocco)
Toronto Metropolitan University (Canada)
University of Nigeria (Nigeria)
Bilim Organization for Research and Social Studies (Afghanistan)
Uniwersytet Warszawski (Poland)
Migration Matters EV (Germany)
University of Sousse (Tunisia)
SPIA UG (Germany)
University of Glasgow (UK, Associated Partner)